

Appendix A3

Semi-structured interviews tracks

A3.1 Firms producing fruit juices and essential oils

- Check which is the main production line (fruit juice or e.o.), whether the production lines are divided and in which order processing takes place (fruit juice first and then e.o. or vice versa)
- Type of citrus fruits used for processing (both for e.o. and for fruit juices - including lemons) and results obtained
- Raw material selection criteria (if any, with particular reference to cultivars and quality standards)
- Origin of raw materials (and distance between citrus fruit harvesting site and processing company location)
- Presence of direct contacts/agreements with citrus growers or intermediaries' involvement
- Main criticalities in raw material sourcing and processing - in general and according to the specific product (focus on citrus fruit seasonality and seasonality of fruit juice and essential oils production and also check if they stock the product (e.o.) even out of season)
- Any pre-processing treatments (including peel cleaning) and storage of raw materials and effects on the production of essential oils
- Type of essential oil extraction
- Main characteristics of the e.o. they obtain (distinguished by type of citrus or type of citrus mix they offer and with reference to chemical composition - if possible)
- Quality standards, if any, to be met to sell the e.o. for human use and impact on production costs
- Market trend (demand) of the types of essential oils (if consumers prefer certain essential oils, they might also transfer this preference to oils used as supplements for animals. Especially if you imagine a relationship between animal nutrition and sensory aspects -i.e. mainly taste- of processed products. (cf. different taste of pasture-raised vs. barn-raised meats and cheeses)
- Type of intended use of the e.o. (cosmetics, nutraceuticals, herbalism, etc.) [and any differences according to intended use].
- Any quality certifications or strategies for product characterisation
- For e.o.: presence of supply chain agreements, sales to large-scale retail trade or direct trade with end users
- Type, amount and destination/use of waste produced
- Any information on other companies producing essential oils
- Main critical issues in the production of e.o.

A3.2 Feed producers – focus on small ruminants

- What are the main processes used to produce feed (apart from pelleting)? What are the main characteristics of these processes? For example, what temperatures or pressures are reached?
- Does the company carry out microencapsulation? How much does the microencapsulation process affect the cost of the final product? How is the microencapsulation introduced into the feed? Does it still have to be pelleted?
- What feed supplements are currently used in feed preparations? What type of supplements are they? What are the technologies and processes used for their processing? Are any essential oils currently used as supplements? [ed. We ask this question to find out if there are any types of supplements with a similar nature to essential oils].
- Do the most popular feeds currently have an expiry date? How long, on average, can they be stored? Does the addition of feed supplements influence (or could influence) the expiry date of the feed (if so, positively or negatively - depending on the type of supplement)?
- Is there a price difference between feed with supplements/additives compared to conventional feed? If so, approximately how much is this price difference?
- Is there demand from farmers for feed with supplements? If yes, which types are most in demand? [editor's note: the question aims to find out how much feed with additives is actually used and demanded].
- Does the company suggest including particular supplements in the diets of small ruminants? If yes, which supplements are recommended? Are they always recommended or only under particular conditions/situations? Which ones?
- To whom are feed supplements sold? Directly to farmers or are there associations/consortia that act as intermediaries?
- How do you promote and differentiate feed products? How many types of products does your company produce? [ed. question is about diversification in a broad sense, both product and label].

[Introduction of the possible benefits of the application of essential oils] According to recent studies, the addition of essential oils as supplements in ruminant diets could have immune and animal welfare benefits.

- Are you familiar with essential oils? Do you think it is possible to include them in animal feed as supplements? What types of essential oils are used and why? Do you have any information on the use of citrus essential oils in animal feed?
- Do you think it is possible to add essential oils before feed processing? What influences the feasibility of such addition? What could be the main critical issues? - In particular, we are interested in information on pellets and microencapsulated, but also on any other transformations/technologies/processes suggested by companies.

- Might a different level of skills/manpower/machinery be needed to include essential oils in feeds?
- Do you foresee a cost difference due to the addition of essential oils in feed? If yes, how important? How much could it weigh/affect the final price of the product?
- What are the cost factors of microencapsulation (at process level)? [not at laboratory level, but the impact of microencapsulation on the cost of the final product].
- Are there substances already used as microencapsulates in the ruminant sector?

A3.3 Veterinarians / Agronomists in charge of food rations

- What are the current diets of sheep? Are there any 'commonly' administered dietary supplements? If so, why are they administered? What are the advantages? Are there also disadvantages or possible side effects?
- (If applicable) Could you give us an estimate of the amount and type of antibiotics commonly administered to sheep? What are the main pathogens and diseases to which sheep are susceptible?
- Is there seasonality in the need to administer antibiotics? If yes, can you tell us about this?
- Are there differences between the nutritional needs of sick and/or nursing animals compared to healthy ones? Do these differences vary with the seasons? And according to the type of animal (e.g. mothers, lambs, lactation, pregnancy)?
- What are the indirect costs of disease? (e.g. organisation of the barn, need to create separate rooms, more labour needed to administer treatment, increased frequency of veterinary visits for sick animals, etc.).
- Are there, in your experience, ways to apply feed supplements to pasture? If so, which ones? How feasible are they? Are farmers inclined to use them?

[Introduction of possible benefits of the application of citrus essential oils in sheep farming] According to recent studies, the addition of citrus essential oils as supplements in ruminant diets could have immune and animal welfare benefits.

- Do you think the application of citrus essential oils could be effective in enhancing the immune response and welfare of sheep?
- Would you include or recommend the inclusion of citrus essential oils as feed supplements in sheep diets? If yes, only at specific times or always? [personal acceptance of citrus essential oils as additives].
- Are you aware of any side effects that may result from the administration of citrus fruits (and/or essential oils in general) to sheep? [with reference also to citrus paste, have any problems been detected from its administration?]
- What are the main critical issues and technical difficulties related to the administration of food supplements and the control of diet and ration according to the type of farming?
- Could the addition of citrus essential oils influence the palatability of feed rations? If so, how? Could the addition of essential oils increase or decrease the animals' acceptance of the feed? [The answer can be based either on one's own belief/opinion or on direct experience].
- Do you think farmers would be willing to use feed supplements based on essential oils in sheep diets? Do farmers usually accept or reject new proposals (either related to animal nutrition or more generally - e.g. new types of drugs)?

- NDR: if you were to interview an agronomist in charge of feed rations: Do you think that through the use of essential oils there is a better chance of meeting the requirements of eco-scheme 1?
- Is *ClassyFarm* widespread in the sheep sector?

A3.4 Sheep farmers

- Type and size of herd; comparison with other herds in the area (with respect to type and size of herd, profitability, etc.)
- Type of products and marketing channels
- Average farm production (milk and/or other products)
- Whether they process milk on the farm
- Who they get for the sheep diet (veterinarians, agronomists, zootechnicians etc.)
- How they obtain feed (directly from the producing industry, area representatives, cooperatives/consortia etc.)
- Method of mixing and administering rations
- Possible administration of additives/feeds containing additives (what types, methods, purposes, occasions of administration, average price of supplements used etc.)
- Perception of the functionality (efficacy) of additives in ensuring animal welfare and increased yields
- Criticality in the administration of additives (and control of the diet and feed ration) according to the type of farm [technical difficulty]
- Animal health: how often do they have sick animals; what are the main diseases and illnesses on their farm (and, if known, on farms in the area)
- Use of vaccinations and against which problems
- Main causes of antibiotic use
- Level of use of antibiotics to treat animals (specify at least how many times a year they have carried out treatments, on how many animals, and then relate this to the size of the herd)
- Animal welfare: impact and extent of heat stress (and any changes in recent years), main issues impacting animal welfare in their context.
- Presence of cooling solutions on the farm and/or intention to implement them
- Attitude and willingness to pay for a heat stress supplement
- Knowledge and opinion on *Classyfarm*; possible membership/willingness to join; real/expected benefits
 - Introduction of essential oils, main benefits/expected benefits
- General opinion (not regarding application to sheep) on citrus e.o. and e.o.
- Experiences, if any, on the use of e.o. (or essences not in e.o. form) as supplements for sheep

- Opinion application e.o. of citrus fruits in sheep: do they think it can be used? In what form (e.g., pelleted, microencapsulated, etc.)? Would it be worth it in terms of cost/benefit ratio? Do they believe in the expected benefits of citrus e.o. or do they consider it ineffective?
- Willingness to use e.o. and o.a. as additives for sheep (in general and if advised by a technician, veterinarian, feed company representative etc.)
- Perception of animal reaction to citrus e.o. additives (Could animals show rejection of feed rations containing citrus e.o.? Have they had experience with the introduction of citrus or citrus e.o. into sheep diets?)
- Expectation regarding the cost impact of adding e.o. in feed, willingness to pay a price difference for feed with added citrus e.o.
- 'All things being equal, having two similar feeds with the same price, differing only in the presence of citrus essential oil supplements in one of them, which one would you prefer?' → how much more [or less] would you be willing to pay for the feed with the additives based on essential citrus oils? (e.g. proposing increasing %:+5% +10%, +20%, +30%

Notes: In this document, supplements and additives are used as synonyms.

A3.5 Sheep products' consumers

- Type of sheep products consumed (sheep/ lamb meat, fresh/seasoned cheese)
- Preferences about sheep products (certifications on animal welfare, quality, igp/dop/etc., mode of purchase [supermarkets, direct from producer])
- Beliefs about the use of antibiotics in sheep farming
- Interest in animal nutrition and welfare, opinions and beliefs about the use of supplements in animal diets (without specifying which ones, whether they consider them positively or not, what they mean/what they think 'supplements' are)
- Expectations regarding the sensory characteristics of products from animals given supplements (both in general and in particular in sheep farming)
- *Classyfarm* system: introduction. Are they familiar with it? Have they ever heard of it? Do they think it could be an important and positive attribute for products? Would they recognise a price difference for products from companies that adhere to Classy farm?

Essential oils.

- Preferences towards citrus fruits and their e.o., presumed effects etc. (to see if there is a positive/negative bias towards citrus e.o., which disregards their use as supplements in animal diets)
- Expectations with respect to the sensory characteristics of the product obtained with e.o. supplements (what they expect it to be like) (also to detect if there is a difference in preferences due to the use of different citrus fruits) - both in general and specifically in sheep farming (both meat and cheese and wool, possibly)
- Preferences towards the product obtained (how they would like it to be)
- Beliefs regarding the effect of the use of e.o. and citrus e.o. additives on animals
- Any citrus fruits preferred as e.o. additives in animal diets and sheep specifically
- Information about the possible effect of reduced antibiotics and increased welfare: does it change preferences? Do they believe this to be true?
- Willingness to pay a higher price for sheep products from animals that have received e.o. additives (i.e. -> all things being equal, having two similar products with the same price, which differ in the use of citrus e.o. supplements in animal feed, which would you prefer?' → how much more (or less) would you be willing to pay for such products? (e.g. proposing increasing %: +5% +10%, +20%, +30%)